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ANALYSIS OF THE INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE OF SUGAR SWEETENED BEVERAGES' TAXATION

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Abstract

One of the most effective policy instruments for curbing the excessive consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages is the imposition of taxes on their production and consumption, a strategy predominantly advocated by the World Health Organization (WHO). The rationale underlying the WHO's recommendation is that a specific tax should be levied on all products with a high sugar content, with the resulting revenue ideally allocated to initiatives aimed at promoting the production and consumption of healthier alternatives, particularly fruits and vegetables.

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the international experience of sugar-sweetened beverage (SSB) taxation across various countries, regions, and jurisdictions. The study was carried out in the context key elements of tax mechanism such as the types of taxes implemented, tax bases, rates, and other variables. Also, taxation models of different international organizations were analysed. In particular, the approaches of international health organizations were investigated. Additionally, the study identifies and discusses the core principles and fundamental components necessary for designing an effective SSB tax system, with particular emphasis on the potential applicability of such mechanisms in Armenia.

Keyword: SSB, WHO, tax, excise tax

Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs) as beverages containing added free sugars, which include carbonated and non-carbonated soft drinks, fruit and vegetable juices, powdered or liquid concentrates, flavored waters, energy and sports drinks, ready-to-drink teas and coffees, as well as fruit juice concentrates.

A substantial body of research has established a strong association between regular consumption of SSBs and an increased risk of adverse health outcomes. For example, the Action on Sugar study found that 79%

of 330 ml carbonated beverages contain six or more teaspoons of sugar, which is equivalent to the maximum daily sugar intake recommended for adults [16].

Furthermore, the habitual consumption of one or two servings of sugary beverages per day has been linked to a 26% increase in the risk of developing type 2 diabetes [28] and a 20% higher likelihood of metabolic syndrome [17]. According to the WHO, nearly 2 billion people worldwide are overweight [2]. The global obesity epidemic is estimated to result in approximately \$2 trillion in annual healthcare costs and economic losses, equivalent to about 3% of the world's gross domestic product [29].

The excessive intake of sugary beverages is also

contribute to elevated blood pressure, an increased incidence of certain cancers, and a higher prevalence of dental caries in children, all of which contribute to diminished health and quality of life [7].

One of the most effective policy interventions to mitigate the overconsumption of SSBs is the imposition of taxes on their production and sale, a strategy strongly advocated by the WHO. The taxation of SSBs has garnered significant attention from policymakers worldwide due to its dual potential to improve public health outcomes and generate additional government revenue [34].

Literature review

The ideological leader of SSB taxation is the World Health Organization that has published numerous researches on that topic. Basically, the WHO arrives at the following conclusion: a separate tax should apply to all high-sugar products and the resulting proceeds should be used for enhancement of production of more useful products, first of all - fruits and vegetables. It should be noted that, as it has been stated already, the WHO attributes to the group of high-sugar products not only drinks excessive in sugar content, but also natural fruit juices that, in some instances, have higher sugar content than SSB drinks [9].

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends levying taxes on sugar-sweetened beverages as part of the updated list of cost-effective and evidence-based policy, in compliance with the WHO Global Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of NCDs 2013–2030 [36]. They represent the "3 wins" strategy, namely – the public health wins, the government revenues win and the health equity wins.

The WHO has developed a manual on the policy of taxation of sugar-sweetened beverages to promote health nutrition. The works aimed at developing comparable metrics for taxation of sugar-sweetened beverages commenced in year 2016 in the WHO's region for the Americas, where the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) has adapted the WHO's method by developing the policy of taxation of sugar-sweetened beverages and the tax level indicators. In 2022, the World Bank launched the regularly adjusted *global sugar-sweetened beverage tax database* [42] that contains information on tax planning and provides for the respective legislation.

An expert advisory group developed the Nutrient Profile Model of the **Pan American Health Organization (PAHO)** to be used as a tool for designing and implementing prevention measures and various regulatory policies.

The proposed model of taxation is mainly focused on sugar-sweetened beverages because of high sugar content and the underlying health risks. The model assesses sugar-sweetened beverages based on nutrient thresholds to determine their impact on health. For sugar-sweetened beverages, the model applies as follows:

➤ **Sugar content:** Nutrient Profile model assesses these beverages as per sugar content – if more than 10% calories of the beverage contain added sugar, the beverage will be qualified unhealthy.

➤ **Labeling and marketing:** Stricter labeling requirements will apply to beverages that contain added sugar, including the use of warning labels or front-of-pack nutrition labels.

➤ **Taxation and restrictions:** the model supports levy of taxes on sugar-sweetened beverages to reduce consumption of the latter.

➤ **Public health campaigns:** aimed at promoting consumption of healthier alternatives such as water or sugar-free beverages.

Taxation of sugar-sweetened beverages according to the Nutrient Profile model is based on the following logic:

Step 1: Data acquisition, analysis, classification of the beverage as unhealthy or healthy.

Step 2: Policy implementation – tax justification, setting of the tax rate, revenue distribution.

Step 3: Monitoring and assessment: assessment of consumption patterns and transformation of the product ingredients.

The Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has developed a comprehensive report [43] that analyzes the impact of taxation of sugar-sweetened beverages and contains the appropriate recommendations. Reducing the use of sugar-sweetened beverages with the help of taxation is a promising response on the part of public health to the obesity epidemic in the USA. This research quantifies the healthcare and economic benefits expected from imposition of the 0.01 USD/oz excise tax on sugar-sweetened beverages. What matters most is that the proposed excise tax of 0.01 USD/oz for sugar-sweetened beverages will result in price increase by 16%, which is much higher than the current tax rates [19].

Most likely, over the short-time horizon the policy of taxation of sugar-sweetened beverages will reduce excess weight both among the young people and the older generation, while increasing potential revenues for health promotion. Within a ten-year period, the policy will reduce healthcare costs and increase health life expectancy. Imposing the mentioned tax can also be a powerful social cue to cutting down consumption of sugar by means of additional changes in individual behavior and policy.

Research methodology

To conduct a thorough analysis of sugar-sweetened beverage (SSB) taxation, several key sources are utilized. The first category includes organizations such as the World Cancer Research Fund (WCRF), the World Health Organization (WHO), and the Global Food Research Program (GFRP). These entities focus on tracking the implementation of tax policies but generally provide limited detail regarding the specific structure of SSB taxes. Their emphasis is often on taxes supported by evident medical rationales and relies heavily on reports from healthcare stakeholders. Consequently, these sources offer limited utility for comparative analysis and the development of nuanced tax policy frameworks.

In contrast, the SSB Global Tax Database, developed by the World Bank, is designed to address these deficiencies. It offers an extensive compilation of veri-

fied data on SSB taxes across the globe. This open-access tool is intended to support scholarly research, increase awareness of policy decisions, and facilitate the formulation of best practices in SSB taxation. Thus, the World Bank database serves as the principal source for our study, providing a comprehensive overview of global SSB tax implementation and structural specifics [40].

Sugar-sweetened beverage (SSB) taxation represents an additional fiscal measure applied to a subset of food and beverage products. The principal types of taxes imposed on SSBs include:

- **Excise Taxes:** These taxes are generally considered the most effective mechanism for mitigating the consumption of unhealthy foods, as they are applied specifically to individual products, thereby increasing their prices relative to healthier alternatives. For instance, the excise tax rate applied to unsweetened bottled water can be utilized as a comparative benchmark for SSBs.
- **Import Taxes:** Levied on goods entering a country, these taxes may impact SSB prices if they exceed rates applicable to other products.
- **Value Added Tax (VAT) or Goods and Services Tax (GST):** These general indirect taxes are applied as a percentage of the product's value and can affect a wide range of goods and services. In the context of SSB taxation, VAT or GST is relevant only if the rate applied to SSBs is higher than that imposed on other food and beverage items.
- **Sales Taxes:** Applied to the sale of goods and services, these taxes are typically calculated as a percentage of the retail price. Sales taxes on SSBs are pertinent when their rates surpass those applicable to other items.

Excise taxes are often preferred for their targeted approach, which can effectively influence consumer behavior by increasing the relative cost of SSBs compared to healthier options [26] (the excise tax rate applied to unsweetened bottled water as an indicator for beverages was considered). Other tax instruments, including import taxes, VAT or GST, and sales taxes, are generally applied more broadly across a range of goods and services and are included in SSB taxation considerations only when their rates are elevated compared to those applied to other food products.

The analysis of SSB taxation by country was conducted using the World Bank's comprehensive database¹. Descriptive analysis was carried out employing Python and Microsoft Excel. Python, recognized for its powerful analytical capabilities, is extensively used for scientific computing, data analysis, machine learning, and modeling. It provides a range of libraries and tools essential for conducting robust research.

The research process utilizing Python was executed through the following steps:

- **Formulation of Research Questions:** Establishing clear objectives and delineating the primary research issues.
- **Identification of Data Sources and Collection:** Importing relevant libraries, such as Pandas, for data management and analysis.
- **Data Preprocessing and Transformation:** Applying libraries like Pandas and NumPy for data cleaning and transformation tasks.
- **Descriptive Data Analysis and Model Development:** Utilizing Scikit-learn for modeling and Matplotlib for statistical visualization.
- **Analysis and Presentation of Results:** Employing Matplotlib, Seaborn, and Plotly to generate maps, diagrams, and tables for effective result presentation.
- **Dissemination of Results:** Publishing findings on GitHub to facilitate accessibility and further research.

The analysis was conducted across several critical dimensions:

a. Global SSB Tax Coverage: This dimension assesses the extent to which sugar-sweetened beverage (SSB) taxation has been adopted across countries and regions worldwide.

b. Tax Instruments: This element explores the various fiscal instruments employed in the taxation of SSBs, such as excise taxes, value-added taxes (VAT), and sales taxes.

c. Tax Structure: The tax structure analysis examines the mechanisms by which tax liabilities for SSBs are calculated, focusing on whether taxes are based on criteria such as product volume, sugar content, or other variables.

d. Rate Structure: This dimension evaluates whether a uniform tax rate is applied to all taxable products or whether differentiated rates are employed, contingent upon product characteristics such as sugar concentration or beverage category.

e. Taxable Goods: This aspect identifies which products are subject to taxation and which are exempt, analyzing variations across product categories and regions.

Regional comparisons were conducted following the World Bank's classification of countries by income groups, enabling a nuanced comparison of SSB tax policies across diverse economic environments [12].

Analysis

1. Tax rates and taxation mechanisms for SSBs.

A) Global coverage of SSB taxes.

The experience of 132 countries applying SSB taxes as of August 2023 was studied, including 115 excise taxes, 9 import taxes, 6 VAT/GST and 2 regional or regional sales taxes. In total, 119 national SSB taxes and 13 subnational taxes are in force in 119 countries and territories (Figure 1).

¹ Data was published on August 2023.

Figure 1. SSB tax coverage worldwide, August 2023

National SSB taxes operate in countries covering more than half of the world's population, including 56% of people living in low- and middle-income economies. Two-thirds (67%) of people in low-income economies and three-quarters (73%) of people in lower-middle-income countries are "covered" by national taxes, compared to less than a third (29%) in upper-middle-income countries.

Table 1.

The share of the population of the countries applying SSB taxes in the total population structure of the regions

Region	Percentage of the population
South Asia	98%
Latin America and the Caribbean	81%
Africa	80%
Europe and Central Asia	41%
Middle East and North Africa	21%
East Asia Pacific	10%
North America	0%

According to the data in Table 1, population coverage of SSB taxa is highest in South Asia (98%), Latin America and the Caribbean (81%), and Africa (80%), compared to Europe and Central Asia (41%), Middle East and North Africa (24%) and East Asia and the Pacific (10%). 8 out of every 10 people in South Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, Africa live in a country with a national SSB tax.

Figure 2. SSB tax coverage by income groups

According to the World Bank's classification of income groups, 34.1% of countries applying SSB taxes are considered high-income (Figure 2), 26.5% are lower-middle income, 22.7% are upper-middle income, 13.6% are low-income countries. The remaining 4 are unclassified territories (Cook Islands, Niue, St. Helena, Wallis and Futuna).

Table 2 presents the list of the 10 countries that introduced SSB taxes the earliest and the latest among the countries under consideration. Accordingly, for the first time SSBs taxes were applied in Brazil in 1965.

Until 2022, some legislative changes were made, according to which the tax rate was reduced.

Russia, Romania and the Grenada region are among the latest countries to use SSB. In particular, the Russian Federation in 2023 made an amendment to the tax code, which established a volumetric excise tax for drinks sweetened with added sugar, sugar syrup or honey, which contain more than 5 grams of sugar per 100 ml, in the amount of 7 rubles per liter, with the exception of juice and milk-based drinks.

Table 2.

List of countries by earliest and latest SSB tax introduction years

<i>Country/Territory</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Country/Territory</i>	<i>Year</i>
Russian Federation	2023	Brazil	1965
Grenada	2023	Niue	1969
Romania	2023	Sao Tome and Principe	1976
Timor-Leste	2023	Yap, Federated States of Micronesia	1985
Newfoundland and Labrador, Canada	2022	Kosrae, Federated States of Micronesia	1985
Zimbabwe	2022	Fiji	1986
Guinea-Bissau	2022	Marshall Islands	1989
Poland	2021	Uruguay	1990
Nigeria	2021	Paraguay	1992
British Columbia, Canada	2021	Netherlands	1992

B) Tax instruments

The majority of SSB taxes are excise taxes, which are applied in 115 of the countries under review, or 87.1% of the sampled countries and territories. In 9 of the countries, SSB taxes are taxes on imports, in 6 countries they are value added taxes, and in 2 countries they are sales taxes (Figure 3).

Figure 3. SSB tax instruments by frequency of application

It should be noted that excise taxes are considered the most effective health tool, since they can target goods that are considered the most dangerous from the point of view of human health protection and raise their prices compared to other goods and services.

A tax that creates a price difference between SSBs and more "healthy" substitutes (for example, unsweet-

ened bottled water), may change the supply and demand for these products. Some excise taxes apply to all soft drinks, regardless of whether they are sweetened or not. In this case, there is actually no shift in demand towards more preferred products.

C) SSB excise tax structure and base

Excise taxes can be applied as special, ad valorem or mixed (hybrid) taxes (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Methods of applying excise taxes on SSBs by observed countries/territories

Special excise taxes are levied in a fixed amount in a form based on certain consumption indicators. SSB tax liabilities can be determined based on sugar content, product volume, or a combination of the two (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Breakdown of the basic principle of calculating the excise tax base by country or territory

Excise taxes based on sugar content (5.19%) are more preferable because they create incentives on the supply and demand side to switch to low or zero sugar substitutes. However, only 4 countries apply SSB taxes specific to pure sugar content: Botswana, Cook Islands, Mauritius and South Africa. Accordingly, in most cases of application of special excise taxes, the volume of

sales of goods is taken as the tax base (89.61% or 69 countries).

Ad valorem excise taxes are charged as a percentage of the value of the goods. This type of tax applies in the case of 41.67%. Mixed or hybrid excise taxes include both special and ad valorem components (11.36 %):

Figure 6. Categories of excise tax rates

Excise taxes can be applied at a single (fixed or linear) rate or using differentiated (multi-level) rates without a tax threshold (the level of sugar content below which the tax is not paid) (Figure 6). In more than half of the current tax cases under consideration, SSBs are applied according to a differentiated model (in 66 countries and territories). One third of multi-level excise taxes are applied at differentiated rates set by sugar content thresholds.

A well-known example of a tiered tax based on sugar thresholds is the one on soft drink manufacturers in the United Kingdom:

- £0.18 per liter (0.25 US dollars) if the total sugar content in 100 ml is 5-8 g;
- £0.24 per liter (0.34 US dollars) if the total sugar content in 100 ml exceeds 8 g.

In the case of 52 tiered taxes, a distinction is made depending on the type of beverage, with most tax jurisdictions using the nomenclature of the Harmonized Commodity Description and Coding System (HS) of

the World Customs Organization to define beverage categories.

In the six countries/territories under consideration (Bangladesh, Cameroon, French Polynesia, Liberia, Madagascar, Tanzania), a gradual rate is applied with differentiation depending on the place of production. Generally, higher rates apply to energy drinks, carbonates, liquid and powder concentrates that can be converted to SSB, while lower rates apply to fruit juices, milk-based beverages and low-calorie sweetened beverages (otherwise called diet, sugar-free or drinks without artificial sweeteners).

D) Taxable goods

The range of main types or groups of goods to which current SSB taxes apply include:

- carbonated drinks,
- energy drinks,
- concentrates and syrups
- sweetened juices
- flavored milk
- unsweetened juices.

Figure 7. Range of product groups subject to SSB taxation by frequency of application

Figure 7 shows the range of SSB taxed product groups according to the frequency of application. It can be noticed that in almost all cases the SSB tax applies to carbonated and energy drinks. In 71 percent of cases observed, the tax is applied to liquid and powder concentrates used to make SSBs, and almost 65 percent of

SSBs are applied to sweetened fruit and vegetable juices.

It is noteworthy that in a significant number of cases, unsweetened juices and flavored milk (sweetened milk-based drinks) are also included in the list of product groups subject to special taxation. Moreover,

these beverages are more often taxed in low- and middle-income countries than in high-income countries.

In general, 3 out of 4 SSB taxes worldwide are applied to diet beverages (low/zero calorie sweetened beverages) that do not contain free sugars. It is also important to highlight that 1 in 4 SSB taxes worldwide are applied to unsweetened bottled water. In low-income countries, this accounts for more than half of SSB taxes.

SSB taxes applied to non-SSBs, such as unsweetened bottled water, would be less likely to cause a price differential between SSB and these healthier alternatives, and thus would be less effective in discouraging SSB consumption.

Overall, the study shows the widespread use of SSB taxes in countries with very different levels of development. It should be noted that the opponents of SSB taxation are commercial organizations engaged in the production and sale of sweet drinks. The economic argument against introducing taxes is the potential impact on the economy and employment, as well as small business operations. In this regard, a clear justification of the health and social benefits of introducing taxes on sugary drinks is an important issue. In some countries, such taxes have been introduced along with other measures to improve nutrition or raise awareness of the dangers of excessive sugar consumption.

International best practice shows that an effective SSB tax system is provided by the complementary effect of the following 4 main mechanisms:

1. Increase in retail prices
2. Raising public awareness
3. Encouraging non-price responses (e.g. product redesign)
4. Acquisition of additional budget revenues, which can be used for the implementation of public welfare improvement programs.

Accordingly, taxing sweetened beverages to effectively promote health improvements can be viewed in the following five-step logic of impact:

1. imposing a tax should increase the price of the target product;
2. the price increase should lead to a decrease in the consumption of the product,
3. reducing product consumption should lead to reduced sugar intake
4. reducing sugar intake should lead to healthier dietary choices
5. healthier dietary choices should improve health and alleviate the associated economic burden.

Conclusion

Taxation of sugary drinks is one of the most effective among the proposed mechanisms in terms of reducing the impact on health. When justifying the choice of the method of taxation of sweet drinks, one should take into account the universal approaches proposed by the WHO, taking into account a number of factors that will help ensure the effectiveness of the taxation mechanism, the realization of economic and social goals. The method of taxation of sweet drinks may depend on the peculiarities of the given economy. Different countries

may have different approaches depending on their economic, social and political situation. Accordingly, it has its influence in the priority areas for the economy.

The analysis of tax rates and taxation mechanisms for sugary drinks (SSB) allowed the following conclusions to be made:

✓ SSBs tax is applied in 132 regions, 10 countries have started applying it in the last three years.

✓ SSB national taxes operate in 119 countries and cover 52% of the world's population.

✓ Population coverage of SSB taxes is highest in South Asia (98%), Latin America and the Caribbean (81%) and Africa (80%).

✓ 34.1% of SSB taxes are applied in high-income countries, 26.5% in low-middle income countries.

✓ Most of SSB taxes are excise taxes (87.12%: 115), with 46.97% special, 41.67% ad valorem. Special taxes are preferable to other taxes because they raise the price of all taxed goods in the same way, are not subject to industry price manipulation, are generally easier to administer, and provide more stable revenues.

✓ Tax liability for SSB taxes is determined by volume in 89.61% cases. Volume-based excise taxes can be implemented more simply than sugar-based excise taxes, providing an effective means of raising revenue.

✓ Excise taxes based on sugar content are 5.19%. Although they are preferable because they create supply-side and demand-side incentives, they can encourage consumers to switch to healthier alternatives, while encouraging producers to reformulate their products (lowering sugar content) to avoid higher tax rates. However, only 4 countries apply specific SSB taxes for net sugar content: Botswana, Cook Islands, Mauritius and South Africa. Two countries, Poland and Sri Lanka, apply hybrid taxes based on a combination of sugar and volume. Accordingly, in most cases of application of special excise taxes, the volume of product sales is accepted as the tax base (89.61% or 69 countries).

✓ Excise taxes can be applied at fixed or differential (multilevel) rates /66 regions/,

✓ 99% of SSB taxes are applied to carbonated and energy drinks (most categories under HS category).

Well-designed fiscal policies, when implemented in conjunction with other policy actions, have significant potential to promote healthy diets that will improve diet-related risk factors, helping to reduce the economic burden. The strongest evidence for taxing sugary drinks in this model boils down to the following idea: reduce consumption by the same percentage as the tax rate.

Thus, research shows that with good processing and correct application, the taxation of sweet drinks leads to an increase in their retail prices and a decrease in the volume of sales and purchases of taxed drinks. At the same time, they refute arguments by opponents of the tax that reduced demand for these drinks will hurt businesses, lead to job losses and slow economic growth, citing the net positive economic effects of taxing sugary drinks, including overall increases in employment and productivity.

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